

3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-Methyl-triazene-N-Oxide—A New Reagent for the Gravimetric Determination of Cu(II)

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3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-Methyl-triazene-N-Oxide as a ligand has been used in the gravimetric determination of 2-30 mg Cu(II). The chocolate brown complex, $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$, is precipitated in the pH range 5-10, adjusted with aqueous ammonia and is weighed as such after drying at 110-120°. Interferences caused by Fe^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , As^{3+} , Sb^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} could be overcome using suitable masking agents. Anions such as F^- , PO_4^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} , BO_3^{3-} , SCN^- , tartrate, oxalate and citrate do not interfere. The average relative error is $\pm 0.49\%$ and relative standard deviation is $\pm 0.38\%$. The reagent has also been used in the determination of copper in alloys.

A critical examination¹⁻⁵ of the important gravimetric methods for the determination of Cu(II) with organic reagents indicates that procedures described have either poor selectivity and sensitivity or cover narrow pH range. In this communication, we recommend a new reagent, 3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-Oxide which reacts with copper(II) quantitatively in the pH range 5-10 forming chocolate brown thermally stable complex $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$. Though the reagent is not highly selective for Cu(II) but the conditions have been set to precipitate the metal ion only in presence of a large number of foreign ions. The reagent is highly sensitive as because even 2 mg of copper(II) in 200 ml could be estimated. Moreover, the procedure is simple, covers a wide pH range, consumes less time and successfully applicable in the determinations of the metal in its several alloys.

Experimental

3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-methyltriazene-N-Oxide : The reagent was prepared following the procedure as described for its isomer⁶. A light yellow crystalline compound obtained after recrystallisation from ethanol melted at 175°. Analysis result : Found C = 56.2%, H = 5.6%, N = 21.96%, Calc. C = 55.95%, H = 5.74%, N = 21.75%.

Cu(II) Solution : A standard solution of Cu(II) was prepared by dissolving electrolytically pure copper in nitric acid, decomposing excess HNO_3 with conc. H_2SO_4 and taken in double-distilled water. The metal content was determined in the usual way⁷.

Diverse ions : Solutions of other ions were prepared from the chloride or the nitrate salts of cations and from the sodium, potassium and ammonium salts of anions. A few drops of suitable acid

was added to prevent hydrolysis where necessary. The chemicals used were of A.R. quality.

Apparatus : A Cambridge bench model pH meter was used to control the pH values.

General Procedure : To an aliquot of standard solution containing 2.0 mg to 30.0 mg of Cu(II) was added 10 ml of 20% solution of sodium-potassium-tartrate. It was diluted to 200 ml and the pH adjusted around 7.0 with dil. ammonia and hydrochloric acid. The mixture was heated to 80° on water bath and 25 mg-200 mg of reagent solution in 5-10 ml of ethanol was added with stirring. The precipitate formed was digested on a hot water bath for 25-30 min with occasional stirring. The chocolate brown precipitate was then collected on a weighed gooch-crucible (No. 3) washed with hot water followed by 20% ethanol and dried at 110°-120° to constant weight. The metal content of the complex was determined using a factor 0.1419. The results of several determinations of Cu(II) are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF COPPER(II)

Cu-taken (mg)	Weight of the Complex (mg)	Cu found (mg)	Relative error %
2.016	14.30 ; 14.36	2.029 ; 2.037	+0.64 ; +0.82
10.080	70.80 ; 71.20	10.04 ; 10.10	-0.40 ; +0.20
20.160	141.40 ; 142.60	20.05 ; 20.23	-0.54 ; +0.35
30.240	214.00 ; 214.40	30.36 ; 30.42	+0.40 ; +0.59

Procedure in the Presence of Diverse Ions : Solutions containing known amounts of Copper(II) and foreign anion or cation and 1.0-1.5 gm of suitable masking agents were diluted to 200 ml. The pH of the mixture was adjusted around 6.5 and copper(II) was then determined as described under general procedure. Table 2 records the results of one of the several determinations.

TABLE 2—SEPARATION OF COPPER(II) FROM DIVERSE IONS
(Cu-taken : 10.08 mg)

Diverse ions added (mg)	Masked by	Weight of the complex (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Relative error %
Oxalate (100)	—	71.19	10.10	+0.20
Citrate (100)	—	71.92	10.12	+0.40
Tartrate (1,500)	—	71.20	10.10	+0.20
Fluoride (500)	—	70.82	10.05	-0.29
Thiocyanate (200)	—	71.53	10.14	+0.59
Phosphate (50)	—	71.92	10.12	+0.40
Borate (50)	—	70.76	10.04	-0.40
Arsenate (50)	—	71.10	10.09	+0.09
Be ⁺⁺ (100)	NH ₄ HF ₂	70.75	10.04	-0.40
Hg ⁺⁺ (25)	KI	71.92	10.12	+0.40
Cd ⁺⁺ (25)	KI	71.83	10.12	+0.40
Zn ⁺⁺ (25)	Na-K tartrate	71.20	10.10	+0.20
Mg ⁺⁺ (100)	..	70.62	10.02	-0.59
Al ⁺⁺ (25)	..	71.25	10.11	+0.29
Bi ⁺⁺ (20)	..	71.10	10.09	+0.09
As ⁺⁺ (20)	..	71.25	10.11	+0.29
Sb ⁺⁺ (20)	..	71.19	10.10	+0.20
MoO ₄ ²⁻ (25)	..	70.82	10.05	-0.29
Pb ⁺⁺ (20)	..	70.82	10.05	-0.29
WO ₄ ²⁻ (25)	..	71.10	10.09	+0.09
UO ₂ ⁺⁺ (25)	Ammonium Acetate	70.68	10.03	-0.49
Fe ⁺⁺ (25)	NH ₄ HF ₂	71.24	10.11	+0.29

Determination of Cu(II) in Alloys : An accurately weighed amount (200 mg) of the chemically standard alloy was dissolved in dil. nitric acid and heated on a water bath with 2/3 ml of conc. H₂SO₄ till the evolution of sulphur dioxide was complete. The content was cooled, filtered in a 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up to the mark. Estimations of copper were then carried out with the prepared solutions. The results of the determinations of copper in different samples are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF COPPER(II) IN ALLOYS

Samples	Copper certified	Copper found
Brass	67.40%	67.92%
Tin Bronze	77.69%	77.89%
Aluminium Bronze	85.90%	85.84%
Manganese Bronze	57.20%	58.08%

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH and Reagent Concentration : A set of experiments was carried out under stated conditions but with variation of pH. It was observed that the precipitation of Cu-complex commenced at pH 4.0 and was quantitative between 5 and 10. In another series of experiments the pH was fixed around 7.0 and the amount of the reagent was varied. It was found that 1.2 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent was sufficient for complete

precipitation. Below pH 5.0 the precipitation was incomplete and above pH 10.0 the complex became slightly soluble. The complex once precipitated in the given manner is fairly stable, i.e., prolong digestion or digestion over boiling water bath does not affect the metal complex.

Interferences : The determination of copper(II) was not possible in the presence of chromium(II, III), manganese(II), cobalt(II) or nickel(II). Disodium-EDTA and cyanide prevented the precipitation while large excess of citrate, oxalate, thiocyanate and phosphate masked copper(II) partially.

Properties, Composition of the Complex : The Cu(II)-3-(*p*-Acetophenyl)-1-methyltriazene-N-Oxide complex melts with decomposition at 214±1°. The complex is insoluble in water (80°) and in 20% ethanol but soluble in absolute ethanol, methanol, acetone, ether (sparingly), benzene, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. The complex was analysed for copper by iodometric method and nitrogen by Duma's method. The results (Found : Cu-14.18%, N-19%, Calc. Cu-14.19, N-18.72%) obtained were in good agreement with the formula Cu(C₉H₁₀O₂N₃)₃, assigned to the complex.

Precision and Accuracy :

The average relative error in the determination of copper(II) by the procedure described was ±0.49% while the relative standard deviation was ±0.38%.

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